

EARTH SCIENCES

VEGETATION COVER MONITORING BASED ON NOAA/AVHRR DATA

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Abstract

Data on vegetation cover over vast territories cannot be obtained based on traditional in-kind measurements due to the lack of a specialized observation network. Point measurements of vegetation parameters at different times do not allow tracking its dynamics, where the “from the particular to the general” method is not applicable. Under these conditions, the only source of information on the state of vegetation cover is space imagery data, which makes it possible to simultaneously monitor the state of vegetation cover over large areas and periodically repeat these observations.

Conservation of biological diversity, ensuring a sustainable state and scientifically based use of vegetation cover objects is possible only with the availability of operational vegetation monitoring. The article describes the developed technology of automated monitoring of vegetation cover based on data delivered from the NOAA/AVHRR series satellite.

Keywords: monitoring, vegetation cover, NOAA/AVHRR, reflectivity, primary processing, thematic processing, vegetation indices, vegetation area.

Introduction

Up to now, there is no permanent network for monitoring the state of vegetation in Uzbekistan. Therefore, the only source of information for diagnosing the state of vegetation is remote sensing data - satellite data. The use of these data for monitoring vegetation is possible only if there is technology for an automated system for diagnosing vegetation on a satellite image. The implementation of this technology in operational mode is possible only if there is a station for receiving satellite information. Uzhydromet has such stations for receiving data from orbital satellites of the NOAA, MODIS series and the geostationary satellite METEOSAT.

Starting from the 60s of the last century, since the development of a new direction in meteorology "Satellite Meteorology" [5,6,8], a wealth of experience has been accumulated in interpreting satellite information in the analysis of atmospheric processes, assessing the state of the environment [14]. The study of the Earth's natural resources, in particular, vegetation cover, is based on measuring the energy and polarization characteristics of the intrinsic and reflected electromagnetic radiation of the studied objects of the atmosphere and underlying surface.

In general, the system of satellite monitoring of natural resources should represent a multifunctional technology with a high level of automation of the processes of receiving and processing information delivered from on board an artificial Earth satellite.

The aim of the work

Development of a technology for an automated system for diagnosing vegetation cover based on

NOAA/AVHRR satellite data for its monitoring in real time.

Used data

Images obtained from the NOAA/AVHRR satellite, covering the territory of Uzbekistan, for the period 2001-2020 (1-2 images per month from April to November), compiled into the developed satellite database and ground-based measurements of the vegetation area in the botanical and geographical region of the lower reaches of the Amu Darya, presented in the work [10].

Physical aspects of remote sensing of vegetation

Diagnostics of vegetation using satellite measurements is based on objectively existing relationships between vegetation parameters and the field of its reflected and intrinsic radiation [9]. The final resulting signal (the formed image field), recorded by equipment installed on the satellite, depends on a large number of factors. Therefore, the solution to the inverse problem - determining the characteristics of the vegetation using the data on the interaction of the electromagnetic field with the vegetation - is not always unambiguous. This ambiguity is eliminated by obtaining the spectral characteristics of a particular plant species by identifying test areas and obtaining the spectral brightness coefficients (SBC) of the vegetation in these identified (reference) areas [Nature, 1984]. The SBC is defined as the ratio of the luminance j_{λ}^{\uparrow} of the outgoing radiation from the vegetation cover in the direction determined by the angles θ, φ , to the luminance j_{λ}^{\uparrow} of the surface scattering equally in all directions (Lambert surface), located in similar lighting conditions:

$$SBC(\lambda, \theta, \varphi) = \frac{j^{\uparrow}}{j_{\lambda}^{\uparrow}} \quad (1)$$

In (1) λ is the wavelength.

The SBC of the vegetation cover and its brightness levels on the satellite image in the infrared (0.7-1.0 μm) and red regions (0.6-0.7 μm) of the spectral ranges of wavelengths are connected by a high correlation dependence [2,12]. The same relationship is observed between the SBC and the vegetation index NDVI [13]. The ratio of the RED n NIR indicators allows us to clearly separate and analyze vegetation from other natural objects. The use of not a simple ratio, but a normalized difference in the form of the vegetation index NDVI

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED} \quad (2)$$

increases the measurement accuracy, reduces the influence of such phenomena as differences in the illumination of the image, some types of cloudiness, haze, absorption of radiation by the atmosphere, etc. The NIR and RED spectral regions are the most stable (they do not depend on other factors). The red region of the spectrum contains the maximum absorption of solar radiation by the chlorophyll of higher plants, and the infrared region contains the region of maximum reflection of the cellular structures of the leaf. That is, high photosynthetic activity (usually associated with dense vegetation) leads to less reflection in the red region of the spectrum and more in the infrared. The characteristic curve of the reflectivity of vegetation as a function of wavelength is shown in Fig. 1a. The NDVI scale is also shown there (Fig. 1b).

Fig. 1. Vegetation reflectance characteristic curve according to NOAA/AVHRR data (a) and NDVI scale (b).

Automated vegetation monitoring technology based on satellite data

Vegetation monitoring is a system of observations of the state of flora and the environment in which they grow, as well as assessment of their changes in order to preserve biological diversity, ensure a sustainable state and scientifically sound use of flora.

The absence of a permanent vegetation monitoring network in Uzbekistan with an area of 448,900 km^2 , on the one hand, and the need for vegetation monitoring, on the other hand, indicate that satellite data are the only type on the basis of which the task can be solved.

The solution to the problem of developing operational vegetation monitoring is divided into two main blocks: a block of primary processing of scanner images from satellites and a block of thematic processing. Fig. 2 shows a general block diagram of the automated vegetation monitoring system.

Primary processing. During the primary processing of the image, geometric distortions due to the curvature of the Earth, systematic radiometric and, if possible, atmospheric distortions are removed from the data. All these distortions are eliminated by the GIS modules of the ENVI package - software for image processing and analysis, which is an industry standard and basic technology for ecosystem analysis [4].

Elimination of distortions in the image allows it to be converted into a form most correct for automated analysis, and is used to highlight the most informative features of the studied object in the image and, as a result, improve the results of thematic processing.

The distorting effect of the atmosphere on the results of scanner measurements from a satellite consists of a complex transformation of the spectrum of reflected and intrinsic radiation, a change in the structure of the outgoing radiation field of the vegetation cover.

In general, the distorting effect is manifested in an increase in the brightness of dark objects and a decrease in the brightness of light objects. Taking into account the factors that contribute to atmospheric distortions is a complex task, the solution of which requires knowledge of a set of atmospheric parameters that affect radiation transfer, namely, the chemical composi-

tion, concentrations and distribution functions of aerosol particles by size, and the concentration of gaseous components of the atmosphere. Research in the field of atmospheric optics, carried out by a number of scientists [11], allows us to conclude that it is possible to eliminate this distortion based on the application of radiation transfer theory [7].

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the technology of automated monitoring of vegetation cover based on satellite data.

Transformation of the image into a given cartographic projection. As a result of transforming the image into a given cartographic projection, a proportional correspondence of the sizes of objects in the image and the earth's surface is achieved. The system provides for stereographic and Mercator projections. Geographic referencing of image pixels can be performed in two ways: using orbital data [5,6] and using reference points [1]. It should be noted right away that the accuracy of referencing using orbital data is inferior to that using reference points due to the fact that in the first case such orbital characteristics as nutation and precession, which are necessary in analytical expressions for referencing using orbital data, are absent. The

results of the primary processing of the image are presented in Fig. 3.

Thematic processing. The automated vegetation diagnosis technology for monitoring purposes was tested on satellite images included in the database.

After calculating the NDVI index (Fig. 4) according to the block diagram shown in Fig. 2 (thematic processing block), classification by NDVI gradations is performed. For this purpose, the procedure for constructing a "Raster Color Slice" [4] for a given number of classes is implemented. Taking into account the NDVI scale (Fig. 1b), the number of classes was set at 16. The results of this procedure are shown in Fig. 5. The same figure shows a histogram of the NDVI distribution.

Fig. 3. NOAA/AVHRR satellite image 12.06.2020 (1 channel), after primary processing – a); б) – synthesized from three channels.

Fig. 4. NDVI distribution for a fragment of the AVHRR image 12.06. 2020.

Note: the border of Karakalpakstan* is outlined in red. The «bird» in the «Slices» scale marks the NDVI values belonging to the «vegetation» class.

The area S_i occupied by vegetation, calculated based on the values of the vegetation index $NDVI > 0.07$, is calculated based on the number of pixels N_i for the given gradation of the accepted botanical-geographical zoning (Fig. 6), multiplied by the pixel size corresponding to the spatial resolution of the NOAA/AVHRR equipment, i.e.

$$S_i = 1.1 \times 1.1 \times N_i \text{ km}^2 = S_i \times 100 \text{ ha}, (i = 1, 2, 3, 4). \quad (3)$$

* The boundary is highlighted because the validation of the vegetation area estimate calculated from NDVI values was performed using available field data for the Lower Amu Darya Karakalpakstan [10].

In our case, for the reason stated in the footnote, the area of vegetation cover was calculated for the Lower Amu Darya region (Fig. 6, i = 3).

Fig. 5. Raster color slice of NDVI of the NOAA/AVHRR image of 06.12.2020, constructed according to 16 classes and a histogram of NDVI distribution.

Fig. 6. Botanical-geographical zoning of Karakalpakstan [3].

Fig. 7 shows the calculated biomass areas in June for the specified botanical and geographical region based on NOAA/AVHRR satellite images for the period 2001-2020. The same figure shows a graph of the dynamics of the area occupied by tugai vegetation species, constructed based on field data from the work [10] for the period 1960-2000. The authors of this work estimate the area with tugai, relative to the total biomass of the Lower Amu Darya, at 67%. It turned out that the graph of the change in the area under tugai vegetation

species is approximated with high accuracy by a 7th degree polynomial with the determination coefficient $R^2 = 0.996$:

$$S = 3.41722618737601E+017 - 1.19648860428514E+015 \cdot Y + 1.795398064186.95 \cdot Y^2 - 1496699390.12214 \cdot$$

$$Y^3 + 748606.902914347 \cdot Y^4 - 224.656251443158 \cdot Y^5 + 0.0374545761391231 \cdot Y^6 - 2.6761392132062E-006 \cdot Y^7, (4)$$

where predictor Y is year.

Fig. 7. Areas occupied by tugai vegetation in the territory of Karakalpakstan in the lower reaches of the Amu Darya, according to natural data (1960-2000) and calculated from NOAA/AVHRR (2001-2020) satellite images.

As follows from Fig. 7, the graphs of the dynamics of the area under tugai vegetation obtained by extrapolating the field data for 2001-2020 by a polynomial and calculated based on satellite information are qualitatively close enough. In absolute values, they also do not differ much, despite the fact that this difference is facilitated by many obvious factors. In general, the results of vegetation cover diagnostics based on satellite images reproduce its dynamics with satisfactory accuracy.

Conclusions

The technology of automated vegetation cover monitoring presented in this article, based on spectral remote sensing data, based on the validation performed at the system testing stage, was introduced into operational work in the agrometeorology department of the hydrometeorological center of the Uzbek Hydrometeorological Service.

This study was carried out within the framework of grant IL-5221091475 «*Innovative technologies for assessing and monitoring the resource potential of vegetation in Karakalpakstan*»

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